

AN INTERESTING CASE OF RAISED RIGHT SIDED PRESSURE – WHAT IS IT?

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Abstract

Keywords:

Pulmonary renal syndrome, small vessel vasculitis, pulmonary embolism, procalcitonin in small vessel vasculitis.

We report case of a 47-year-old lady who presented to the emergency room with sudden onset breathlessness for 4 hours. The clinical, laboratory, EKG and 2D Echo were all suggestive of pulmonary embolism and hence was taken up for immediate thrombolysis, however treatment modalities were inverted as she developed headache, epistaxis and worsening of preexisting hematuria. In view of rapidly rising creatinine, worsening breathlessness possible diagnosis made were acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), pulmonary edema (Cardiogenic/ non Cardiogenic) and pulmonary renal syndrome. Finally after narrowing down the diagnosis of renal vasculitis and thoroughly ruling out sepsis/ septic focus, patient was started on IV pulse steroid therapy and immune-modulators. The condition of the patient improved substantially with improvement in clinical and lab parameters.

I. Introduction

Small vessel vasculitis presenting as pulmonary renal syndrome is a clinico- pathological entity and can closely mimic clinical symptoms of pulmonary embolism. The role of thrombolysis in a fluid responsive hypotension patient with clinical features (Well's score), 2D Echo, EKG and laboratory investigations suggestive of pulmonary embolism without radiological evidence can be risky. Moreover serum Procalcitonin can be raised even in small vessel vasculitis. Small vessel vasculitis leading to pulmonary renal syndrome is a serious life threatening condition, which closely mimics pulmonary embolism and needs prompt management. Early use of I/V steroids would be an effective management and hence needs a strong clinical judgment.

II. Case report

A 47 years old normotensive, non-diabetic lady presented to emergency room with complaints of sudden onset shortness of breath for about 4 hours associated with decreased urine output. She had no complaints of chest pain, palpitation, fever or previous history of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), hemoptysis, bronchial asthma, similar episode, DVT or any thrombo-embolic events (stroke, MI, amaurosis fugax, Limb ischemia, recurrent pregnancy loss) in other systems in the past. General examination of the patient, revealed an alert and conscious patient with tachycardia (108/min), B.P (140/80 mmHg), tachypnoea (32/min) and hypoxia (oxygen saturation on room air 85%). Chest examination revealed bilateral basal fine crepts. Other systemic examination was unremarkable. Initial blood investigations revealed deranged leukocyte count (N-95, L-4, M-1), TLC – 12.7, Blood Gas analysis (pH:7.30, pCO₂:30mmHg, pO₂:55mmHg, Lac:1.3mmol/L, Hct:32%, HCO₃⁻: 14.8mmol/L, BE(B): -10.5 MMOL/l, BE ecf :-11.6mmol/L) and rapidly worsening kidney function (Creatinine - 2.97, 4.25, 3.97, 4.7), Troponin I -249.7 and NT-PRO BNP – 10628, D-DIMER- 3.68ug FEU/ml. Urine routine and microexamination revealed active urinary segment, (RBC ++, protein ++).

Image 1a **Image 1b** *CXR revealed hazy bilateral mid zone, lower zone and CP angle (image 1a). ECG revealed sinus tachycardia with ST-T changes with S1, Q3, T3 pattern (image 1b).*

ECHO revealed RA/RV dilatation with PASP 90mmHg, LV global hypokinesia with EF – 55%, no intra-cardiac clot, vegetation, pericardial effusion and IVC collapsing more than 50% associated with mild MR/TR. CTPA was avoided in view of worsening kidney function. Modified Well's score and Clinical Probability of Pulmonary Embolism (PERC) for Clinical Probability of Pulmonary Embolism (5) was calculated and in high suspicion of PE patient was started on systemic thrombolysis (I/V.Inj. Streptokinase 25000IU infusion). However patient developed severe headache, epistaxis and hence thrombolysis was stopped after 15 minutes. NCCT Head ruled out any intraparenchymal bleed, epistaxis and was managed conservatively however hematuria persisted (before and after thrombolysis). There was no improvement in clinical scenario as well as in serial blood investigations. Parameters in context of PE associated with impending respiratory arrest secondary to respiratory fatigue and increasing trend of creatinine persisted and hence patient was revised for other differentials which were acute onset MODS with worsening of pulmonary, renal and cardiac system, ARDS, pulmonary edema (Cardiogenic/NonCardiogenic), pulmonary renal syndrome with underlying capillaritis associated with underlying vasculitis.

HRCT THORAX Image 2a **Image 2b** **Image 2c** *HRCT (Image 2a, 2b) revealed significant diffuse alveolar opacities associated with ground glass haze and air bronchogram in bilateral lung right from the apex up to the base with borderline cardiomegaly and mildly dilated pulmonary artery features suggestive of pulmonary hemorrhage and pulmonary edema. Lung ventilation-perfusion scan (Image 2c) was within normal limit.*

Vasculitic – blood work up revealed elevated ESR, ANA (anti nuclear antibody) - weak positive (sample: serum, Dilution: 1:100, Technique: Indirect immune fluorescence assay) and pANCA – positive (sample: serum, Dilution: 1:20, Technique: Indirect immune fluorescence assay). cANCA anti GBM ab, anti phospholipids antibodies (IgG, IgM), cardiolipinab (IgG,IgM), Lupus anticoagulant C3, C4 levels were normal and hence Wegener's granulomatosis, Good pasteur syndrome, and Antiphospholipid syndrome were ruled out . (4) Serial serum

Procalcitonin (PCT) was done which was initially normal and then showed an increasing trend. However all blood investigations were negative in favor of sepsis and therefore we reiterate the fact that elevation of serum PCT level is well documented in cases of inflammation (vasculitis) as well. The patient was started on intravenous pulse Cyclophosphamide 50mg once daily, with I/V Solumedrol 250mg once daily for 3 days and then changed to T. Prednisolone 30mg twice daily. In view of anuria and rising creatinine and uremic symptoms she was started on hemodialysis. Serial serum PCT follow up revealed a decreasing trend. Plasmapheresis was initiated as per protocol (ref) and patient showed remarkable improvement. She started producing urine with improvement in clinical symptoms, hematological, kidney function (creatinine), ESR values and *radiological imaging (image 3)*.

III. Discussion

The triad of hemoptysis, diffuse alveolar infiltrates and low hematocrit, defines pulmonary renal syndrome (1,2), however the presentation can have a wide spectrum and can range from typical to atypical presentations commonly considered as Isolated RPGN, Diffuse alveolar hemorrhage, Pulmonary artery hypertension, Acute Cor pulmonale (1).

The underlying cause of pulmonary renal syndrome is usually systemic vasculitis, (4) which is predominantly small pulmonary and renal vessels. In the lungs Diffuse alveolar hemorrhage (DAH) is caused by pulmonary capillaritis and rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis (RPGN) involves damage of capillaries and basement membrane with leakage of erythrocytes followed by influx of macrophages, fibrinogen and formation of extra capillary cell proliferation called crescents. In 80% of ANCA associated pulmonary renal syndrome has detectable ANCA by ELISA and by immune-fluorescence. In our case the diagnosis of RPGN was made in view of rapid progressive renal failure, proteinuria, hematuria, high ESR, pANCA positivity with normal complements and normal anti GBM. A renal biopsy would have been gold standard however our patient and relative did not consent for the procedure. Negative CTPA and VQ scan (Image 2a, 2b, 2c) ruled out pulmonary artery hypertension and pulmonary embolism. Modified Well's score and clinical probability of pulmonary embolism (PERC) are internationally accepted for clinical algorithm of pulmonary embolism (5). In our case the calculated score was positive and hence was started on thrombolysis. However in patients with normal hemodynamic (normal BP, HR, mental status, capillary refill, absent mottling, skin temperature, urine output), high PCT values (3) in pulmo-renal syndromes might rather reflect severe organ damage of lungs and/or kidneys than sepsis and hence blunt the initiation of pulse steroid therapy and redirect our diagnosis towards sepsis, ARDS, (non Cardiac edema) MODs (6, 7, 8) if not interpreted in context to the case. Hence timely administration of steroid, immunosuppression and plasmapheresis can save the kidney.

IV. Conclusion

Approach to patient of sudden onset breathlessness should not be limited to ARDS, pulmonary edema, pulmonary embolism, non-Cardiac/Cardiac shock. Small vessel vasculitis involving renal and pulmonary vessels should also be considered as early diagnosis and prompt management is extremely rewarding in such cases (2).

Moreover with a rising number of renal transplants in the world the chances of occurrences and recurrence in transplanted kidneys are not well documented in literatures and therefore need further study to elucidate the role of ANCA levels in the evaluation and treatment of small vessel vasculitis involving renal and pulmonary vessels. (9,10)

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